

VIRTIGATION – Emerging viral diseases in tomatoes and cucurbits: Implementation of mitigation strategies for durable disease management

Deliverable 2.3 Protocols for full genome sequencing

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Lead beneficiary:	KU Leuven
Author:	Hervé Vanderschuren: herve.vanderschuren@kuleuven.be Victor Golyaev: victor.golyaev@kuleuven.be
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XYZ	Approval	Victor Golyaev: victor.golyaev@kuleuven.be
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The logo for Virtigation, featuring a stylized red tomato slice and a green leaf icon above the word "Virtigation" in a bold, sans-serif font.

Protocols for full genome sequencing

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ToBRFV: Tomato brown rugose fruit virus

ToLCNDV: Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus

TYLCSV: Tomato yellow leaf curl Sardinia virus

RCA: Rolling circle amplification

SNP: Single nucleotide polymorphism

SRS: Short read sequencing

D2.3, D2.4: Deliverable 2.3, Deliverable 2.4

KUL: Katholieke Universiteit Leuven

CSIC: Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas

EW: Emweb

CTAB: Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide

PVP: Polyvinyl pyrrolidone

EDTA: Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid

NaP: Sodium phosphate

1 PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The deliverable 2.3 (D2.3) compiles the protocols for full length genome sequencing of circular DNA and linear RNA viruses designed to study virus populations, their diversity, geographical distribution and evolution.

In order to develop protocols for full genome virus sequencing *Cucurbitaceae* (*Cucurbita pepo*) and *Solanaceae* (*Solanum lycopersicum*) plant samples infected with Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (ToLCNDV), Tomato yellow leaf curl Sardinia virus (TYLCSV) and Tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV) were collected by **CSIC** and **KUL**.

The protocols allow for the in-depth profiling of DNA and RNA virus populations in infected plant samples in 3 steps: 1) Enrichment of viral RNA and DNA, 2) Virus sequencing using Oxford Nanopore technology, 3) Sequencing data analysis with the Genome Detective online analysis tool designed by EW (D2.4).

2 INTRODUCTION

Tomato and cucurbit crops are affected globally by emerging risks associated with diseases caused by plant viruses. For diagnostics and rapid mitigation of emerging diseases reducing the vegetable crop yield, Virtigation D2.3 designed the protocols that allow in-depth profiling of DNA and RNA virus populations in infected plant samples in 3 steps: 1) Enrichment of viral RNA and DNA, 2) Virus sequencing using Oxford Nanopore technology, 3) Sequencing data analysis with the Genome Detective online analysis tool designed by EW (D2.4). The designed protocols have been successfully implemented for detection of full-length viral genome sequences in *Solanaceae* (*Solanum lycopersicum*) and *Cucurbitaceae* (*Cucurbita pepo*) plant samples infected respectively with the begomovirus Tomato yellow leaf curl Sardinia virus (TYLCSV) or the tobamovirus Tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV) for the solanaceae samples, and with begomovirus Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (ToLCNDV) for the cucurbitacea samples. The protocols were successfully tested for detection of full-length virus sequences in the plant samples collected in the field and greenhouse.

3 PROTOCOLS FOR VIRUS FULL GENOME SEQUENCING

The deliverable 2.3 (D2.3) compiles the protocols for full length genome sequencing of circular DNA and linear RNA viruses designed to study virus populations, their diversity, geographical distribution and evolution. In this section, we describe two pipelines that allow in-depth profiling of DNA and RNA virus populations in infected plant samples in 3 steps: 1) Enrichment of viral RNA and DNA, 2) Virus sequencing using Oxford Nanopore technology, 3) Sequencing data analysis with the Genome Detective online analysis tool designed by EW (D2.4).

3.1 Pipeline for full genome sequencing of DNA viruses

Figure 1. Pipeline for full genome sequencing of circular DNA viruses

The designed pipeline generates and profiles high-quality full genome sequences of circular ssDNA virus variants in 3 steps. This protocol is adequate for begomoviruses (<https://viralzone.expasy.org/111>) either monopartite like TYLCV, or bipartite like ToLCNDV. First, viral circular DNAs enriched from the total DNA sample by rolling circle amplification (RCA) (Protocol 1) are sequenced with the latest R10.4.1 Nanopore sequencing kit (Protocol 2). The long RCA viral reads are then deconcatenated by TideHunter tool (1) to produce highly accurate intact viral full-genome sequences. Finally, viral sequences are clustered based on their similarity, random errors corrected and quantified by Genome Detective online tool (D2.3). The complete bioinformatics pipeline starting from deconcatenation step is implemented into Genome Detective web interface that allows users to directly upload the raw Nanopore data and profile ssDNA virus variants in the samples.

Protocol 1

Leaf tissue samples (50 mg) were homogenized in 2 ml Eppendorf tube by grinding in 1 ml of CTAB buffer (pH=8) using a sterile pestle. The homogenate was mixed twice with an equal volume of chloroform: isoamyl alcohol (24:1) and centrifuged at 10k rpm followed by collection of the aqueous phase. The total DNA was precipitated with 0.6 volume of isopropanol and 0.1 volume of sodium acetate 3M (NaOAc pH 5.2) at -20°C for 1 hour, recovered by centrifugation at 12k rpm for 20 min at 4°C , washed twice with 70% ethanol and air-dried in a bio-cabinet.

High-quality viral DNA for sequencing was prepared with Circular DNA enrichment (CIDER) method (37). Briefly, extracted total DNA (20-50 ng) was enriched for circular DNAs by randomly primed circular DNA amplification (RCA) at 30°C for 18 h in a reaction containing: 1×Phi29 DNA polymerase buffer, 1 mM dNTPs, 50 μM Exo-resistant random primer, 0.02 U inorganic pyrophosphatase, and 10 U Phi29 DNA polymerase. The amplification products were purified by precipitation with 1/10 volume of 3M Sodium Acetate, 20mg/ml molecular biology-grade glycogen and 2 volume of 100% Ethanol, debranched via non-primed Phi29 amplification with 5U of Phi29 DNA polymerase at 30°C for 2 h and linearized by treatment with 50 U S1 endonuclease at 37°C for 30 min. Debranched DNA was purified by precipitation with 1/10 volume of 3M Sodium Acetate, 20mg/ml molecular biology-grade glycogen and 2 volume of 100% Ethanol.

Protocol 2

TYLCSV Viral DNA was sequenced using an ONT MinION Flow Cell (R10.4.1). First, debranched dsDNA sample (~1000 ng) was mixed with the components of NEBNext FFPE DNA Repair and NEBNext Ultra II End Repair/dA-Tailing modules and incubated at 20°C for 15 mins followed by enzymes inactivation at 65°C for 5 mins. Subsequently, DNA was cleaned using the AMPure XP Beads followed by adapter ligation with Nanopore Ligation Sequencing Kit v14 according to the manufacturer protocols. Prepared libraries (~200 ng) were loaded into the Nanopore flow-cells (R10.4.1) according to the manufacturer instructions and sequenced for 48-72 hours using MinKNOW software. Reads basecalling was performed with Guppy (v6.5.7) using super accuracy algorithm (dna_r10.4.1_e8.2_400bps_sup).

Figure 2. TYLCSV virus variants detected by the pipeline using raw and duplex Nanopore data.

The sensitivity of the pipeline allowed the profiling of TYLCSV virus population, including the detection of single nucleotide variations in their full-length genome sequences with frequency as low as 1% (Figure 2 and 3).

Figure 3. The relative frequencies of TYLCSV virus variants and corresponding SNPs detected in duplex Nanopore data and three additional variants exclusively reconstructed from raw Nanopore data.

While the pipeline based on raw data enabled reconstruction of three additional variants (Variant-11, Variant-12 and Variant-13) with single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) confirmed by SRS (Figure 2 and 3), the other 124 reconstructed virus variants containing 101 SNPs were not confirmed by short read sequencing (SRS). Thus, despite of the higher sensitivity for virus variant reconstruction, the accuracy of the pipeline based on raw reads was not enough to distinguish between real mutations and sequencing errors without validation by SRS. The use of duplex reads increased the overall quality and accuracy of the analysis as illustrated by the detection of only “true” TYLCSV virus variants which were confirmed by SRS (Table 1).

Table 1. Number of TYLCSV full-length virus variants detected in raw and duplex datasets.

Dataset	TideHunter (min. number of copies)	TYLCSV full-length variants	Confirmed TYLCSV variants	False positive SNPs	False negative SNPs
Raw data	2	137	13	101	0
Duplex data	2	10	10	0	3

3.2 Pipeline for full genome sequencing of RNA viruses

Figure 4. Pipeline for full genome sequencing of RNA tobamoviruses.

The designed pipeline generates and profiles high-quality full genome sequences of RNA tobamoviruses in several steps. First, virions are extracted from grinded plant leaf tissue followed by viral RNA extraction (Protocol 3 and 4). In the case of the tobamovirus chosen, the genome has a 5' cap structure (m7G5'pppG) and the 3'-terminus has a tRNA-like structure (<https://viralzone.expasy.org/51>), consequently for the sequence analysis the extracted viral RNAs are polyA-tailed, decapped and converted into full genome cDNAs by smart-RT-PCR using oligo-dT30VN and TSO primers (Protocol 5, Table 2). The full genome cDNAs are amplified by PCR using IS-PCR primer (Protocol 6, Table 2) and viral dsDNAs are sequenced with the latest R10.4.1 Nanopore sequencing kit (Protocol 2). The raw Nanopore sequencing reads are processed to trim the adapter and primer sequences using Porechop tool (<https://github.com/rrwick/Porechop>) and errors in homopolymeric regions are corrected with LoRMA tool (2). Finally, viral sequences are clustered based on their similarity, random errors corrected and quantified by Genome Detective online tool (D2.3) (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Bioinformatics pipeline for profiling of full genome sequences of RNA tobamoviruses.

Protocol 3

The virions are extracted by adding 1 ml of Buffer A (0.5 M Sodium phosphate (NaP), pH 7, 0.1% beta mercaptoethanol) to each gram of tissue powder and vortexing the mixture thoroughly. An equal volume of a butanol/chloroform mixture (1:1) is added, and the solution is mixed by shaking for 1-2 minutes. The mixture is then transferred into 2 ml tubes and centrifuged at room temperature for 10 minutes at 13.3k rpm. The upper aqueous phase is carefully collected and subjected to another round of centrifugation at 13.3k rpm for 15 minutes. The upper aqueous phase is then taken and mixed with 0.1 volume of 40% PEG8000. This mixture is incubated on ice for 10 minutes and subsequently centrifuged at maximum speed for 10 minutes. The supernatant is discarded, and the resulting pellet is resuspended in 0.2 volume of 10 mM NaP buffer, pH 7. The suspension is centrifuged at 5000g for 10 minutes, and the supernatant is transferred into a fresh tube. To the supernatant, NaCl is added to a final concentration of 1%, and PEG8000 is added to a final concentration of 4%. The mixture is centrifuged at maximum speed for 10 minutes, after which the supernatant is removed. The final pellet is resuspended in 10 µl of 10 mM NaP buffer, pH 7.

Protocol 4

Total RNA is extracted from grinded in liquid nitrogen ToBRFV-infected leaf material. Mix 5 ml of preheated to 65°C CTAB buffer (mixed with 100 µl of fresh 2-mercaptoethanol) with 0.5 grams of the ground tissue in 15 ml tube and incubate at 65°C for 10 minutes. Add 5 ml of a Chlorophorm:Isoamyl

alcohol (24:1) to the tube and centrifuge at 8,500 rpm for 10 minutes at 4°C. Carefully transfer the upper aqueous phase to a new 15 ml tube, add an equal volume of Chlorophorm:Isoamyl alcohol (24:1) and centrifuge at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4°C. Transfer the aqueous supernatant to a new 2 ml Eppendorf tube, add 0.1 volume of sodium acetate (3 M, pH 5.2) and 0.6 volume of isopropanol, mix gently, and store the tube at -20°C for 1 hour to precipitate the RNA. After incubation, centrifuge the mixture at 12,000 rpm for 20 minutes at 4°C to recover the precipitated material. Wash the RNA pellet with 200 µl of 70% ethanol at 10,000 rpm for 5 minutes and resuspend the pellet in 20-50 µl RNase-free water.

CTAB buffer

300 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.0), 25 mM EDTA (ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid), 2 M NaCl, 2% (weight/volume) CTAB, 2% (weight/volume) polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP), and 2% (volume/volume) b-mercaptoethanol (added just before use).

Protocol 5

1. RNA polyA-tailing

10X E. coli Poly(A) Polymerase Reaction Buffer (NEB)	2 µl
ATP (10 mM)	2 µl
Rnase inhibitor (20 µg/ul)	0,5 µl
E. coli Poly(A) Polymerase (NEB)	1 µl
RNA (up to 10 µg)	15 µl
Incubate at 37°C for 30 minutes	

2. Purify RNA with AmpureXP beads according to the manufacturer instructions.
3. Decapping of ssRNA

10X mRNA Decapping Enzyme Reaction Buffer (NEB)	2 μ l
10 U mRNA Decapping Enzyme (NEB)	1 μ l
RNA (1-1.5 μ g)	17 μ l
Incubate at 37°C for 30 minutes	

4. Purify RNA using a column cleanup kit (Qiagen's RNeasy MinElute Cleanup Kit).
5. Smart RT-PCR reaction

Place reagents into a 0.2-ml thin-walled PCR tube:

RNA	13 μ l
10 mM dNTPs	2 μ l
oligo-dT30VN primer	2 μ l
<p>Quickly flick the tube to mix, spin down the solution and immediately place it on ice.</p> <p>Incubate the samples at 72 °C for 3 min and immediately put the tube back on ice.</p> <p>Spin down the samples and then put them immediately back on ice.</p> <p>The oligo-dT primer is now hybridized to the poly(A) tail of all the mRNA molecules.</p>	

RNA	8,5 μ l
5× reaction buffer (Thermofisher)	4 μ l

TSO primer (10 μ M)	2 μ l
Rnase inhibitor (20 μ /ul)	0,5 μ l
Betaine (5 M)	3,5 μ l
MgCl ₂ (50 mM)	1 μ l
Maxima H Minus Enzyme Mix (Thermofisher)	1.5 μ l
Incubate at 50°C for 1.5h Terminate the reaction by heating at 85°C for 5 minutes	

6. RNase H treatment

RNA	20 μ l
RNase H (5 units)	1 μ l
Incubate at 37°C for 20 minutes and inactivate at 65°C for 10 minutes.	

Protocol 6

1. cDNA PCR

Nuclease-free water	2.5 μ l
cDNA	11 μ l
5X Phusion™ HF Buffer (Thermofisher)	4 μ l
10 mM dNTPs	1 μ l

IS-PCR primer (10 µM)	1 µl
Phusion™ High-Fidelity DNA Polymerase (Thermofisher)	0.5 µl

PCR program

Number of Cycles	Denature	Anneal	Extend	Hold
1	98 °C, 3 min	–	–	–
20	98 °C, 30 s	67 °C, 30 s	72 °C, 6 min	–
1	–	–	72 °C, 5 min	–
-	–	–	–	4 °C

- Clean-up with Ampure XP beads according to the manufacturer instructions.

Table 2. Sequence of primers used

TSO	AAGCAGTGGTATCAACGCAGAGTACATrGrG+G
IS-PCR	AAGCAGTGGTATCAACGCAGAGT
oligo-dT30VN	AAGCAGTGGTATCAACGCAGAGTACT30VN

The pipeline enabled reconstruction of two ToBRFV virus full genome variants from field tomato sample collected in Belgium (Figure 6).

Figure 6. ToBRFV virus full genome variants detected in field tomato sample. ToBRFV virus variants are mapped to ToBRFV Dutch isolate found by Blastn search.

ANNEX 1: REFERENCES

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